

Chemical Composition of the Essential Oil of *Carum anethifolium* Benth.

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A gas chromatography/mass spectroscopy study of the essential oil of *Carum anethifolium* Benth. shows the presence of 11 monoterpene hydrocarbons (80%), 9 monoterpenoids, 6 sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, and 2 sesquiterpene alcohols. Of these, 22 compounds have been identified. The monoterpenes, viz. β -phellandrene, γ -terpinene and *p*-cymene are the major constituents.

THE genus *Carum* includes about 30 species and is distributed in temperate and sub-tropical regions. Four species of this genus in India have been reported, out of which two grow in Nainital^{1,2}, *Carum anethifolium* Benth. is an annual herb and is widely distributed around Nainital, mostly in open and slopy areas³. The physico-chemical properties of the essential oil from *Carum anethifolium* have been reported³ but there has been no report on the chemical composition. However, the work so far reported on the chemical composition of the essential oil from *Carum carvi* shows carvone, thymol, carvacrol and γ -terpinene as the main constituents (in seeds). Our investigation confirmed the absence of carvone and carvacrol, and the presence of γ -terpinene (22.42%) and thymol (1.83%) in the essential oil from *C. anethifolium*. This communication reports the identification of 22 compounds in the oil from *Carum anethifolium* (aerial part).

Experimental

Plant material : *Carum anethifolium* was collected from Nainital in June (before flowering) and August (with flowers). The essential oil extracted in the month of June was taken for determining the chemical composition.

Extraction of oil : The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of the fresh plant material extracted from water with pentane, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent distilled off. The physico-chemical properties of the oil were determined⁴.

Gc analysis : The gas chromatography of oil was performed on Varian 3700 gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector using a 35 m glass capillary column coated with OV-101. The percen-

tage of various constituents was calculated from the peak areas.

Gc/ms analysis : The oil was analysed by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry using J and W fused silica capillary column (coated with DB-5, column dimension 30 m \times 0.25 mm) and He as carrier gas (10 lb in⁻²). The ionization energy was 70 eV. Column temperature was programmed at 2° min⁻¹ from 60° for the first 25 min, 4° min⁻¹ after 25 min and finally isothermally at 225°. The sample was taken in CH_2Cl_2 for injection. At least 28 peaks were recorded in the gas chromatogram from RT 13.10 to 45.05 min. The mass spectra corresponding to the gc peaks were recorded. The mass spectra were compared with the ms of authentic samples and those available in the literature⁵⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

Physico-chemical properties of the oil were : specific gravity 0.8068, refractive index 1.4952, acid value 1.2, ester value 2.5, ester value after acetylation 31.0, and carbonyl value 1.0. The oil yield from fresh plant material was 0.14% and 0.24% during the months of June and August, respectively.

The results of gc/ms analysis of the oil are given in Table 1. Eleven monoterpene hydrocarbons constituted 80% of the oil, β -phellandrene, γ -terpinene and *p*-cymene being the major constituents. Nine oxygenated monoterpenoids accounted for 8.53% of the oil. Six sesquiterpene hydrocarbons form 4.96% of the oil, α -humulene and *trans*- α -bergamotene being dominant among these. Two sesquiterpene alcohols constitute 1% of the oil. Thymol, a phenol amounted only 1.83% while the other phenolic constituents, reported in other *Carum* oils were not detected in this oil.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *C. anethifolium*

Compound	Gc peak	RT min	% in the oil
Monoterpene hydrocarbons			
β -Ocimene-X	1	13.10	2.48
C ₈ H ₁₄	2	13.80	0.13
Myrcene	3	14.20	1.16
α -Fenchene	4	15.23	1.12
<i>p</i> -Cymene	5	16.15	16.08
Limonene	6	16.67	7.08
α -Phellandrene	7	17.98	0.58
γ -Terpinene	8	18.63	22.42
β -Phellandrene	9	20.37	28.34
C ₁₀ H ₁₆	10	22.35	0.53
C ₁₀ H ₁₄	11	24.20	0.08
Oxygenated monoterpenoids			
Myrtenol	12	24.50	3.07
Dihydrocarvone	13	24.87	0.12
Dihydrocumyl alcohol	14	25.88	0.24
C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O (alcohol)	15	26.40	0.27
Carveol	16	26.93	0.21
Thymol	17	27.20	1.83
C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O (alcohol)	18	28.08	0.48
Borneol	19	32.10	1.19
Unidentified (MW 166)	20	37.30	1.12
Sesquiterpene hydrocarbons			
α -Humulene	21	38.67	1.26
Cedrene	22	40.08	0.77
<i>trans</i> - α -Bergamotene	23	40.58	1.51
Aromadendrene	24	41.02	0.60
Cuparene	25	41.08	0.41
β -Bisabolene	26	42.35	0.41
Sesquiterpene alcohols			
<i>trans</i> -Bergamota-2,12-dien-14-ol	27	43.02	0.52
β -Eudesmol	28	45.03	0.48

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